

ISic2995

Inscribed altar or statue base

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

dedication

Material

limestone

Object

altar

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Autopsy

2015.07.03

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Adranon

Place of origin (modern)

Adrano

Provenance

Found by Orazio Cavallaro in 1896, predio del cav. Reale, contrada Ardichella, on the north side of Mendolito, approx. 5km NNW of modern Adrano ; subsequently passed to the Reale family in 1906, and acquired by the museum in 1957 (gift of the Reale family).

Coordinates

37.70611, 14.80968

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Adrano, Museo Archeologico Regionale di Adrano

Physical Description

A quadrangular base of off-white limestone, with a moulding running around all four sides of the bottom edge (now lost on the left side). The upper part of the base is lost. All four sides are smoothly finished, and the front side preserves a Greek inscription of at least 6 lines.

Dimensions

Height 36 cm

Width 54.5 (49.7 excluding the moulding) cm

Depth 40.5 (35.7 excluding the moulding) cm

Layout

The inscribed face is maximum 0.26 m high and 0.497 m wide. The text is extremely irregular and uneven in its layout, with letters of varying size and the horizontal of the lines very erratic. The text appears to observe the left margin with some consistency, but is extremely irregular on the right. The full height of the face is employed: the final line is squeezed.

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

The inscription is crudely engraved and inexpertly laid out on the face. The letter forms are primarily distinguished by their irregularity and the poor quality of the engraving. Theta is formed by large circle with single mid-dot; epsilon on occasion has a shorter middle bar; omega is notable in being consistently extremely open, with short horizontal tails (projecting outwards only); omicron is generally full-size, or nearly so, but also smaller; kappa has equal length arms which join the vertical, but do not generally extend fully to the top/bottom of the line; alpha is broad with straight bar; phi has a rounded closed eye; nu on occasion has a shorter right vertical, leaning outwards; sigma is either four straight bars (with top and bottom strokes open beyond the horizontal) or with the top and bottom strokes joined by a single curving stroke; rho is closed, with either a rounded or an angular eye; pi has a shorter right hasta; mu is in one case faint and compressed, in the other broad and composed of four short off vertical strokes; delta is either regular, or with the

base line angled down to the right.

Letter heights:

Line 1: incomplete mm

Line 2: 20-30 mm

Line 3: 20-23 (phi is 35) mm

Line 4: 17-35 mm

Line 5: 17-28 (omicron is 10) mm

Line 6: 17-25 mm

Line 7: 20-30 mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: 8 mm

Interlineation line 2 to 3: 15-20 mm

Interlineation line 3 to 4: 0-13 mm

Interlineation line 4 to 5: 0-10 mm

Interlineation line 5 to 6: 0-35 mm

Interlineation line 6 to 7: 0-10 mm

Text

1. [](vac.undefined)[---]

2. Θεωδώρα

3. καὶ Φίλωνος

4. ἱεροθύται

5. Νικασίων Εὐπολέμου

6. Νεμήνιος Ἡρακλείδα

7. Ἀγάθων Εὐδάμου

Apparatus

Text based upon autopsy

Orsi: [Ἐπὶ ?]; Manganaro: [Ἐ] ;

Orsi: Ἀράθων

Translation (en)

[--?--] (in the magistracy/priesthood) of Theodoros and Philon. The hierothytai Nikasion son of Eupolemos, Nemenios son of Herakleidas, Agathon son of Eudamos (set this up).

Commentary

Traces of at least two letters are visible at the upper left of the inscribed face (vertical strokes only), with room for one or two letters preceding. Empty space follows, but there may be traces of further letters to the upper right. It is

impossible to know how much has been lost from the top of the block. Confusion in some transcriptions regarding the final letter of line 4 (Εὐπολέμου sometimes read as Εὐπολέμον) is the result of a scratch or unintentional stroke on the stone, which is not part of the final letter.

The names are all very common, attested across the Greek world and in Sicily, with the exception of Νεμήνιος [http://clas-igpn2.classics.ox.ac.uk/cgi-bin/igpn_search.cgi?name=%CE%9D%CE%B5%CE%BC%CE%AE%CE%BD%CE%B9%CE%BF%CF%82], which is distinctively Sicilian (13 out of 16 known instances are Sicilian (add the example at Halaesa in SEG 59.1100 to the 15 in LGPN).

The priestly position of ἱεροθύτης (hierothytes) is also attested in Agrigentum (IGDS I, no.185), Malta (IG XIV, 953), Soluntum (ISic1413 [<http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic1413>]), Segesta (ISic1111 [<http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic1111>]), as well as in a recently found bronze inscription of uncertain Sicilian provenance (IGDS II, no. 76, attributed to Agrigentum). Winand (1990, p. 129-139) discusses all but the most recently found instance, and concludes that while the instance(s) at Agrigentum reflect the colonial Rhodian influence on the city, in the other cases, including Adranon, the origin of the position is likely to be Syracusan influence. The unusual Doric form ἱεροθύτης is only otherwise attested in the recently found bronze inscription (IGDS II, no. 76) and at Rhodes (C. Blinkenberg, *Lindos. Fouilles et recherches, 1902-1914. Vol. II, Inscriptions, 2 vols, Copenhagen Berlin 1941, vol. I, I, nr. 26*).

Already Paolo Orsi (1900, p. 42-43 nr. 1) proposed restoring the word ἐπὶ in line 1, and in this he was followed by Manganaro (1961) and Dubois (IGDS II, no.107). The two vertical strokes visible top left are compatible with this, and the word would be expected in the eponymous dating formula which the two names in the genitive of line 2 imply; the title of these two officials may or may not have appeared at the upper right. Eponymous officials without an explicit title are relatively common in Sicily, and the traces on the stone suggest a significant gap, so that there is no necessary need to restore anything further after the word (see Manganaro 1961, p. 129 n. 13 for discussion of the title ἄρχοντες, and the surveys of Sicilian eponymous officials in R. Sherk, *The eponymous officials of Greek cities V: the register*, in ZPE, 96, 1993, pp. 267-295 and P. Di Veroli, *Nuovi eponimi della Sicilia ellenistica*, in ZPE, 110, 1996, pp. 309-310).

It is impossible to know whether the stone was a statue base or an altar (parallels for both altars (uninscribed) and small bases with similar texts can be found at Akrai, e.g. Bernabó Brea, *Akrai* (1956), p. 139-140; ISic1031 [<http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic1031>], ISic1029 [<http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic1029>] and esp. ISic1024 [<http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic1024>]). In either case, this is likely to have

been a dedication to a divinity by the college of hierothytai and Manganaro (1961, p. 128 n. 9) suggested that it was an altar dedicated to the local divinity Adranos. This must remain speculation, however attractive. It is likely that the name of the deity to which it was dedicated appeared at the top of the inscription, perhaps on the, now lost, upper moulding of the stone.

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